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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“LABS DAKA TATA”

Lugud ing bigkis tamu
At ing Ginu ing kayantabe tamu
Balu ku dakal ko pangarap para kaku
Sasabyan ku naman biguan ali dakayu

Dapot magkasakit ku
At nung mjnsan mabibigu
Kekayung lugud yang magpasikan kanaku
At pasibayu babangun ku para lumaban at ali na mabigu,

Tune pagal at pawas ing puhunan tamu
At talagang iti payalagaan ku
Tagumpe ya kabud, kekayu asuyu ku
At nanuman sang malyari, king Ginu magtiwala tamu.